

Open Health Care UK

Description

Open Health Care UK is a consulting firm that works with clinicians and health care organisations, including the National Health Service (NHS), to develop digital solutions to address the needs of health care providers, seeking to improve efficiency, effectiveness and clinical outcomes through data analytics. In partnership with the Open Data Institute (ODI) and Mastedon C, Open Health Care UK through their Prescribing Analytics project, performed an analysis of publically available prescription data from the NHS related to the prescribing practices of physicians in the UK. This work focused specifically on statins, a commonly prescribed type of medication used to control blood pressure, where both brand name and generic versions are available.

Evidence for both drugs suggests that they are equally as effective, with no discernible difference between products other than the cost absorbed by the health care system, thus doctors are typically advised to prescribe the cheaper of the two. NHS prescription data suggests that on average, an excess of £27 million per month in savings could be achieved if all physicians were to only prescribe the generic version of the drug. This data analysis took only eight weeks to complete and its findings suggest potential annualized savings in excess of £220 million. Open Health Care UK has also developed an analytics platform called OPAL that can be used in a variety of health care settings, employing real time data and measurement to enhance clinical decision making and patient care outcomes.

Economic benefits

£220 million cost savings.

Health/social benefits

Cost saving to NHS would allow funds to be used for other areas.

Supporting links

'Prescription savings worth millions in ODI incubated company'

<http://bit.ly/prescription-savings>

Accessed 24 April 2016.